

RADNEXT Transnational Access Summary Report

Project title	<i>Proton SEE Testing of Candidate COTS Electronic Components for a Space Radiation Monitor</i>
Project TA identifier	TA10-346
General application	Space
Type of test	SEE
Group leader, Institute	<i>Melahat Bilge Demirköz, IVMER (The Research and Application Center for Space and Accelerator Technologies)</i>
Co-authors, Institutes	<i>Melahat Bilge Demirköz, Mehlika Zeynep Arslan, Uğur Kılıç, Hazal Düyen, Samet Amanvermez</i>
Date(s) of the experiment	July 16-17
Facility	UCLouvain- Centre de Ressources du Cyclotron (CRC)
Amount of access granted (unit of access: 1h)	8

Objectives of the experiments

YRM (Home Grown Radiation Monitor) is being developed for operation on satellites and is designed to measure proton flux between 6 and 200 MeV in 8 bins of kinetic energy and trapped electron flux in Low Earth Orbit for 5 years, with a possible upgrade later for deployment on Geosynchronous Orbit. Development models, called SB.0, consisting of 2 energy bins for protons have flown on sounding rockets [1] and the next version, SB.1 with 4 energy bins for protons, is under construction. Commercial -off-the-shelf (COTS) electronic components are planned to be used in YRM to reduce cost. Therefore, Single Event Effects testing and analysis of the critical candidate electronic components is necessary to reduce the operational risk, data loss and loss of communication.

12 of the COTS electronics include two power managers whose product codes are TPS2420RSAT and MAX891LEUA+T respectively, three interface transceivers with product codes PCA82C250T/YM,115, MAX3485AEASA+ and PCA82C250T/YM,115 one interface receiver with product code AM26LS32AIDG4, an interface driver with product code AM26LS31AIDG4, a flash memory with product code MX30LF2G28AD-TI, a sensor with product code LMT01DQXR, a programmable timer with product code SE555DR, an ADC with product code ADC128S102CIMT, a DAC with product code MAX5253BEAP+, alongside with generic transistors and resistors. The components with the specific product codes MAX3485AEASA+ (interface transceivers) and SE555DR (programmable timer) had never been investigated for their readiness to perform in harsh radiation environments.

To predict the SEU rates of candidate components in space and to fit the data to the Weibull function of four variables which describes the dependence of cross section with proton energy, testing of the component's SEU cross section with respect to proton energy from threshold energy to saturation

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energy range at 60-100-150-200 MeV was proposed. A test card containing 12 of the COTS candidate electronic components have been designed. The testing of candidate components with 15 and 30 MeV protons had already been performed at METU-DBL[2]. RADNEXT has granted 8 hours of beamtime at Universite Catholique de Louvain Cyclotron Resource Centre-Light Ion Facility (UCLouvain CRC-LIF) where testing of the 11 of the 12 components has been performed with 60 MeV protons. Since it was decided that PCA82C250T/YM,115 interface transceiver was not going to be used after the tests done with 15 and 30 MeV protons, it was not tested for 60 MeV protons as to not waste beamtime. The results have been analyzed and been compared to the tests done with 30 and 15 MeV protons.

Relevant Publications

- [1] M. B. Demirköz, A. Albarodi, U. Kılıc., A. Can, E. Karadöller, D. Boztemur, M. Aktas, T. Atasever, C. Zorlu, “Design of a Space Radiation Monitor for a Sounding Rocket and Results from the First Turkish Sounding Rocket Flight,” in RADECS., Vienna, Austria, 2021, pp. 1-7.
- [2] E. Karadöller et. al, “METU-DBL: A Cost Effective Proton Irradiation Facility. JINST,” vol.18, no. T06010, Jun., 2023, 10.1088/1748-0221/18/06/T06010.

Experiment test report

Candidate COTS Devices

List of the candidate COTS devices that were tested and information about them are given below

Device Reference	Device Function	Technology Processes
(1) TPS2420RSAT	Power manager	BiCMOS Texas Instruments “lbc7” process Feature size: 350nm
(2) MAX891LEUA+T	Power manager	CMOS
(4) MAX3485AEASA+	Interface transceiver	Feature size: 800nm
(5),(6)AM26LS31AIDG4/AM26LS32AIDG4	Interface driver/ receiver	Texas Instruments “ji” process
(7) MX30LF2G28AD-TI	Flash memory	Macronix “an” process
(8)LMT01DQXR	Temperature sensor	CMOS
(9)SE555DR	Programmable timer	BJT
(10)ADC128S102CIMT	Analog-to-Digital Converter	Texas Instruments “cmls7” process
(11)MAX5253BEAP+	Digital-to-Analog Converter	CMOS
(12)BC857BS,115	Transistor	BJT

Test Setup and Conditions

The SEE test setup consists of a “Control Card” and a “Test Card”. The control card communicates with the test card through UART and SPI interfaces. Using a multiplexer and switching relays, one of 15 addresses which correspond to device under test (DUT) on the test card can be chosen. The control card is built around a PIC microprocessor, DSPIC33CK64MP508, which has 69 I/O pins and CANBUS interfaces as well as 64KB memory and 100 MHz clock speed. The test card and the COTS electronic components that were tested can be seen in Fig. 1.

Figure 1: The Test Card designed 12 candidate components. The component numbers given in Table 1 correspond directly to the numbers given in yellow font on the figure. The components indicated with white font are used during the testing for power management and latch-up *simulations*.

The control card was fed a voltage between 8 V and 12 V via a terminal connector and generated 5.0 V and 3.3 V both for internal use and for feeding the components on the test card. Each power, relay, analog and digital connection is carried using separate connectors between the test card and the control card. The control card includes a MAX6373 watchdog, a LMT01 temperature sensor and RS485 circuits that operates throughout the SEE radiation test. These components function to monitor the DUT’s responsivity and its operational status. The control card has software in MPLAB written in C to monitor the test procedure.

Testing was performed at UCLouvain CRC-LIF with 60 MeV protons. Every component was tested for 1500 seconds with a flux of 1×10^8 protons/cm²/s until a fluence of 3×10^{11} protons/cm² was reached for all components. The beamline delivered to the DUTs after the collimator had an area of 40mm x 40mm with uniformity $\pm 10\%$. Since each component needed to be tested separately, and UCLouvain LIF’s table could only vertically and needed to be controlled manually, a lightweight card holder that could be controlled remotely via Arduino Nano development board and A4988 motor driver module was designed and manufactured to change the test card’s horizontal position with respect to the beam.

Figure 2: The schematic of the remotely controlled card holder.

Dynamic tests were performed on all DUTs with the procedure detailed below.

- Control card was powered on.
- An initialization sequence was sent to establish communication with the control card
- The specific bypass relay for the DUT was activated.
- The current driven by the DUT was checked.
- The control and test cards were powered off.

Testing Measurements and Results

Overall, the objectives of the experiment could mostly be fulfilled. The description of testing measurements for each component and the results are explained below.

A. TPS2420RSAT

A functionality SEE test was performed on this power manager. A latch-up configuration was simulated using resistor blocks. In the regular configuration the resistor block was made to draw 60 mA current, and in the latch-up configuration the resistor block was made to draw 600 mA current. The

two scenarios were simulated successively during the SEE testing. The current drawn from a functional power manager was expected to switch off the resistor block when the latch-up current was simulated and to switch on when the latch-up configuration was over. No functional error was observed during the 60 MeV proton tests which is consistent with the literature where the SEE of the device was investigated for protons with kinetic energies equal to and more than 50 MeV [1].

B. MAX891LEUA+T

The procedure explained in section A for TPS2420RSAT was repeated for this power manager as well. Functional errors were not observed during the tests. The result from the 60 MeV proton test agrees with literature [1].

C. MAX3485AEASA+

This interface transceiver was successively sent control bits “01010101” and the response bits were checked for any discrepancies throughout the tests. During the test with 60 MeV protons the observed MBU number was 342 and the SEU number was 22. The total cross section was calculated to be $(1.22 \pm 0.06) \times 10^{-9} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ for 60 MeV protons. The cross sections and their errors with respect to proton energies (15, 30 and 60 MeV) are shown in blue dots and the 2-parameter Bendel Fit with Bendel parameters [2] are shown with blue dashed line in Fig. 3.

D. AM26LS31AIDG4 and AM26LS31AIDG4

The procedure detailed in section C was repeated for this interface receiver and interface driver duo. 73 MBUs and 24 SEUs were observed during the test with 60 MeV protons and the total SEE cross section was calculated to be $(3.30 \pm 0.33) \times 10^{-10} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ for 60 MeV protons. In Fig. 3, the cross sections and their errors found for all three proton energies (15, 30 and 60 MeV) and their errors with respect to proton energies are shown in orange triangles and the 2-parameter Bendel Fit with Bendel parameters [2] are shown with orange dashed line.

Figure 3: The cross sections with respect to proton energies of MAX3485AEASA+ are shown with blue dots and their 2-parameter Bendel fit is shown with blue dashed line. The cross sections with respect to proton energies of AM26LS31AIDG4/AM26LS31AIDG4 are shown with orange triangles and their 2-parameter Bendel fit are shown with the orange dashed line. The 2-parameter Bendel function parameters are shown on the legend.

E. MX30LF2G28AD-TI

This NAND 2-Gbit Flash Memory with 4 kB page size and 8-bit error correction code was checked for any discrepancies in its response bits to the control bits “01010101” that were sent to it successively during the test. Unlike prior studies done on similar flash memory parts with 2 kB page size and 4-bit error correction

code where SEUs and MBUs were observed [3], no errors were observed during the test for this specific device. An upper limit of $3.33 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ was found for 60 MeV protons.

G. LMT01DQXR

The number of high and low square waves read by this temperature sensor was compared with each other. A difference between the number of high and low square waves different than 0 was accepted to be an indication of an SEE. During the test with 60 MeV protons, no error was observed and an upper limit of $3.33 \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$ was found.

H. SE555DR

In this programmable timer the number of high and low square waves, corresponding to the timer's frequencies, were read and counted by a microcontroller. There was an increase in the difference between the high and low wave numbers during the 60 MeV proton test session where both wave numbers decreased in time. However, the rate at which the low wave number decreased was slower than that of the high wave number. It was observed that the ceramic timing capacitor used for the DUT which was shielded by the shield that had a cut-out of 2.0 cm \times 2.5 cm during the 15 MeV and the 30 MeV proton tests at METU-DBL was exposed to protons during the tests with 60 MeV protons at UCL-LIF where the beam area was 4.0 cm \times 4.0 cm and no shield was used. Upon inspection on the effects of radiation to ceramic capacitors [19], it was suggested that the exposure of the ceramic timing capacitor could be the cause in the difference between the high and low wave numbers. Therefore, the test with 60 MeV protons was inconclusive and further testing is required.

I. ADC128S102CIMT

For this 12-bit ADC the expected value of $2.5 \pm 0.05 \text{ V}$ was compared to the corresponding digital output value 2048. A threshold of 0.05 V was set based on the variations in the expected value found in measurements taken before the test. During the test recorded values above 2.55 V or below 2.45 V was counted as SEU or MBU. No SEUs or MBUs were observed throughout the test with 60 MeV protons.

J. MAX5253BEAP+

This 12-bit DAC was sent bits corresponding to specific 307 mV. The analog voltage readout taken before the test with 60 MeV protons was between 403 mV and 354 mV and these were set as the threshold values during the test with 60 MeV protons. Values above 403 mV and below 354 mV were counted as SEU or MBU. The cross section for the 60 MeV proton test was calculated as $(3.67 \pm 0.11) \times 10^{-12} \text{ cm}^{-2}$.

K. BC857BS,115

The current drawn by this transistor was monitored throughout the tests with 15 MeV, 30 MeV and 60 MeV protons to observe total ionizing dose (TID) effects. The current drawn by the device was observed to be stable during all three test sessions.

These results have been shared during the RADECS 2024 conference in Canary islands with a poster presentation.

To continue the scan of the complete proton energy range (20-200 MeV) as is recommended by ESCC, further testing with higher energy protons was need. Therefore, another proposal was made during RADNEXT's 11th call and a beamtime of 8 hours at the PARTEC Proton Irradiation facility has been kindly granted by RADNEXT.

References:

[1] J. Budroweit, N. Aksteiner, T. Firchau, J. Haseker, "Compendium of current proton-induced radiation effects results on integrated power supervisors," in RADECS., Virtual Conference, 2020, pp. 1-3.

[2] Proton Test Guideline Development – Lessons Learned, NASA, Washington, D.C., USA, 2022, pp 28-33.

[3] "Single-Event Effects Proton Test Report MX30LF4G18AC," Hirex, Toulouse, France, Rep. HRX/SEE/00656, 2017.

Outcome of the experiments

Please indicate what the experiment is likely to lead to by putting an 'X' next to one or more of the possible outcomes below.

Journal publication	x
Data for Thesis	
Follow-up experiment at same facility	
Follow-up experiment at another facility	x
Other	

As a RADNEXT user, we encourage you to submit the scientific results of your experiments to journals as well as to the NSREC and RADECS data workshops. Please remember to include the RADNEXT acknowledgment into your publications!

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